

Synthesis of Thiazoline Compounds and their Mercurated Derivatives. Part II

B. B. Raul and G. N. Mahapatra

Action of *sym.*-di-(*p*-tolyl)thiourea on various ketones and their derivatives has been studied in presence of iodine and the resulting thiazoline compounds have been mercurated. The position of the acetoxymercuri group in the molecule has been ascertained. These thiazoline compounds have been converted into their corresponding thiazolone derivatives. The fungicidal and bactericidal actions of these compounds have also been investigated.

Action of thiocarbanilide on monochloroacetic acid (Lange, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 595; Desai *et al.* *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1935, 54, 118; Klare *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2137) and action of *sym.*-dialkylthiourea on α -haloketones have been studied (Garreau, *Compt. rend.*, 1953, 236, 1575) and the respective formation of thiazolidone and thiazoline compounds has been reported.

Twelve ketones (both saturated and unsaturated alkyl and aralkyl) including one ketonic ester have been condensed with *sym.*-di-*p*-tolylthiourea in presence of iodine. From the mechanism of the action of haloketones on *sym.*-dialkylthiourea (Garreau, *loc. cit.*) and the action of thiourea and phenylthiourea on ketones and iodine (Mahapatra, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 527), the following possibility of the reaction between the components resulting in the formation of 2-(*p*-tolylimino)-3-(*p*-tolyl)-4- or 4,5-di-substituted thiazoline compound has been suggested (Mahapatra, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1957, Part III, 139).

Formation of the thiazoline derivative has been confirmed as follows. When *p*-bromophenacyl bromide was condensed with *sym.*-di-*p*-tolylthiourea in presence of ethanol, 2-(*p*-tolylimino)-3-((*p*-tolyl)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiazoline (m.p. 85°; found S, 7.1; Br, 17.81. Calc. S, 7.35; Br, 18.39%) was formed which was identical in all physical and chemical properties to the compound prepared by condensing *p*-bromoacetophenone with *sym.*-di-(*p*-tolyl)thiourea in presence of iodine.

In the case of unsaturated ketones, like mesityl oxide, the reaction takes the above course, but in the ultimate product no unsaturation remains. The reason for this has been suggested earlier (Mahapatra, *loc. cit.*, 1956).

Presence of the imino group at C₂ is confirmed by the fact that when the compound is hydrolysed with HCl, a thiazolone derivative having a keto group at C₂ results along with *p*-toluidine as the cleavage product. Presence of *p*-toluidine is detected by diazotisation of the filtrate and subsequent coupling with β -naphthol, when a red azo dye separates (m.p. 129°).

These 2-*p*-tolylimino-3-*p*-tolylthiazoline compounds have been mercurated with one equivalent of mercuric acetate and the mercuric compounds so obtained are found to have only one acetoxymercuri group in the *p*-tolyl nucleus attached to the nitrogen at 3-position. The position of the acetoxymercuri group in the *p*-tolyl nucleus in the *o*-position to the nitrogen atom is justified from the earlier observations of mercuration of 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones (Mahapatra and Rout, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 715). The possibility of the acetoxymercuri group entering the *p*-tolyl nucleus, attached to the imino group at C₂ of the thiazoline nucleus, is discarded on the ground that when the mercurated compounds are treated with potassium perbromide solution, monobromo derivatives having the bromine atom attached to the place previously linked to the mercury group are obtained.

These monobromo derivatives on hydrolysis yielded products which were not free from bromine and on analysis found to contain one equivalent of bromine. This indirectly suggests the linking of bromine atom to the *p*-tolyl nucleus attached to the nitrogen atom at 3-position, as shown above. If the bromine atom would have been linked to the *p*-tolyl nucleus attached to the imino group at C₂ position, the bromo compound on hydrolysis would not have retained the bromine atom, which is not the case. This finally confirms the position of the bromine atom and hence the position of the acetoxymercuri group in the *p*-tolyl nucleus attached to the nitrogen atom at 3-position.

Each of the thiazoline compounds, so obtained, has been hydrolysed with HCl in ethanol medium to afford the corresponding 3-*p*-tolyl-4- or 4,5-dialkyl-substituted 2-thiazolinone,

The mercurated and some of the non-mercurated derivatives have been assayed for their fungicidal and bactericidal properties (Table II).

TABLE I

No.	Nature of R ₁ .	Nature of R ₂ .	Thiazoline derivatives (I).				Thiazolone derivatives (II).			
			M.P.	Yield.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	Me	H	93°	85%	10.20	10.89	73°	56%	6.34	6.83
2.	Ph	H	118°	75	9.58	8.99	112°	75	5.50	5.24
3.	Me	Me	75°	70	10.34	10.39	82°	72	6.41	6.39
4.	Me ₂ CH-	H	65°	80	10.04	9.94	72°	58	5.75	6.00
5.	(<i>o</i>)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	83°	63	9.21	8.60	90°	68	5.15	4.94
6.	Me	Bu	82°	73	9.89	9.14	58°	43	6.20	5.36
7.	Me ₂ CH-CH ₂ -	H	63°	67	9.55	9.52	70°	62	5.92	5.66
8.	Me	Et	62°	65	10.38	9.94	72°	63	6.13	6.00
9.	(<i>p</i>) Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	83°	72	6.98	7.35	65°	40	4.72	4.04
10.	(<i>p</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	69°	76	7.80	8.19	62°	45	4.52	4.64
11.	Ph-CH ₂ CH ₂ -	H	93°	85	8.50	8.33	75°	60	4.92	4.74
12.	Me	C ₂ H ₅ OO-	65°	63	8.92	8.74	76°	62	5.20	5.05

TABLE II

No. of comps.	M.P.	Acetoxymercuri derivatives (III).		
		% Yield.	% Mercury.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	165°	58	35.80	36.23
2.	175°	82	32.40	32.57
3.	190°	80	35.54	35.33
4.	215°	82	34.23	34.48
5.	162°	85	32.02	31.74
6.	168°	70	33.21	32.89
7.	194°	75	34.25	33.67
8.	200°	67	34.28	34.48
9.	202°	78	29.20	28.96
10.	159°	62	30.98	30.84
11.	165°	90	31.50	31.15
12.	220°	85	32.35	32.05

N.B. Nature of R₁ and R₂ is the same as in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(*p*-Tolylimino)-3-*p*-tolyl-4-methylthiazoline (I).—A mixture of *sym*-di-(*p*-tolyl) thiourea (5.3g.), acetone (1g.), iodine (5g.), and dry benzene (30 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath for 24 hours and for 6 to 8 hours without the use of condenser after distilling the benzene. The reaction product was kept in contact with ether for 48 hours with occasional stirring with a view to removing the unchanged ketone and iodine, presence of which made the product gummy. After decanting the ether, the crude product was boiled with water (50 c.c.). The water was decanted and the product treated with ammonia (*d* 0.888) to liberate the base. Some of the compounds remained gummy even after treatment with ammonia, but these could be made solid by occasionally scratching the product, keeping it for a

longer time in ammonia (conc.). The product was finally crystallised from EtOH-AcOH, m.p. 93°, yield 85%. (Found: N, 9.11; S, 10.2. $C_{18}H_{13}N_2S$ requires N, 9.52; S, 10.88%).

Mercuration of (I).—The preceding thiazoline (1.7 g.), dissolved in EtOH-AcOH (50:50), was treated with an ethanolic solution of mercuric acetate (2 g. in 30 c.c. of ethanol, acidified with acetic acid). The mixture was stirred with a glass rod and kept for 24 hours till the precipitate appeared. In some cases the precipitate appeared after adding a small amount of water to the mixture. The residue was then collected by filtration, washed thoroughly with hot water, and finally with ethanol and very dilute acetic acid, m.p. 165°, yield 58%. (Found: Hg, 35.80. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_2SHg$ requires Hg, 36.23%).

TABLE III

Bactericidal and fungicidal data of mercurated and non-mercurated thiazoline derivatives.

No.	Bactericidal activity.		Fungicidal activity (% germinations in 10 p.p.m.).	% Germination in the control.	Unmercurated compounds.		
	<i>E. coli.</i>	<i>S. A.</i>			Bac. activity.	<i>E. coli.</i>	% Germination at 10 p.p.m.
1.	1 : 10,000	1 : 10,000	-	-	-	-	-
2.	1 : 10,000	1 : 50,000	25	25	-	-	-
3.	1 : 20,000	1 : 100,000	37	90	-	-	-
4.	1 : 10,000	1 : 20,000	..	..	-	-	-
5.	1 : 50,000	1 : 50,000	..	..	-	-	-
6.	1 : 20,000	1 : 100,000	..	..	-	-	-
7.	1 : 50,000	1 : 20,000	..	..	-	-	-
8.	1 : 50,000	1 : 10,000	..	..	-	-	-
9.	1 : 50,000	1 : 100,000	20	65	-	-	-
10.	1 : 100,000	1 : 100,000	20	85	1 : 1000	1 : 1000	70
11.	1 : 50,000	1 : 50,000	37	90	-	-	-
12.	1 : 50,000	1 : 100,000	16	90	1 : 1000	1 : 1000	80

* The compounds refer to those in Table I.

3-p-Tolyl-4-methyl-2-thiazolone (II).—The thiazoline (1g.) was taken in a conical flask. To this rectified spirit (30 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 4 c.c.) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours, the excess ethanol was distilled, water was added into the flask, and made just alkaline. The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 73°, yield 56%. (Found: N, 6.34; S, 15.13. $C_{11}H_9ONS$ requires N, 6.83; S, 15.61%).